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Exploring the Life Circumstances in Colleen Hoover's It Ends with Us

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Abstract: *This qualitative study analyzed the life circumstances represented in Colleen Hoover's novel It Ends with Us, to understand how literature reflects personal, familial, and social struggles. Anchored on Stephen Greenblatt's New Historicism and Roland Barthes' Reader-Response Theory, the study examined character development, thematic elements, symbolism, and the life values conveyed in the text. Findings revealed that the main characters navigate complex emotional challenges shaped by trauma, abandonment, and the struggle for healing. Lily Bloom's journey reflects the effort to break the cycle of abuse; Ryle Kincaid represents the consequences of unresolved trauma; and Atlas Corrigan embodies resilience and the pursuit of emotional safety. The major themes identified include breaking the cycle of abuse, healing and forgiveness, emotional strength, and the long-term effects of trauma. Symbolic elements such as the flower shop, Lily's name, the journal letters, and the phrase "It ends with us" highlight growth, self-renewal, emotional processing, and generational change. The life values emphasized include courage, self-respect, empathy, responsibility for breaking harmful cycles, and the slow and painful process of healing. Overall, the study underscores the emotional and social relevance of the novel, particularly its contribution to raising awareness about domestic violence and the psychological complexity of abusive relationships.*

Keywords: *Literature, Life Circumstances, Abuse, Trauma, Symbolism, New Historicism, Reader-response Theory*

Introduction

Literature reflects human experiences, including the struggles people face in their personal, family, moral, and social lives. Through stories, readers gain insight into how individuals think and feel, allowing a deeper understanding of others. Modern novels continue to play this role by raising questions about identity, relationships, and the challenges of daily life. Colleen Hoover, a well-known American author of contemporary romance and young adult fiction, has written 22 novels and novellas. Many of her works have appeared in USA TODAY's Top 200 Best-

Selling Books and among the Top 20 Adult Print Bestsellers in 2022, which shows their strong emotional impact and wide readership. Her novels often depict personal hardships, family conflict, emotional struggles, and social pressures, many of which are influenced by real-life circumstances.

Life circumstances refer to the unique personal, social, and emotional situations that influence how individuals respond to challenges, such as relationship difficulties, financial pressures, or emotional distress (Smith 2023). Literature that reflects these struggles allows readers to identify with characters and understand issues that may be difficult to discuss openly. Personal issues involve internal emotional or psychological challenges, family issues relate to conflicts among family members, moral issues involve decisions about right and wrong, and social problems concern broader concerns that affect communities. These issues are often highlighted in literary works to encourage reflection, empathy, and critical thinking. While studies have discussed how literature mirrors human life and its struggles, fewer studies examine how these issues are explicitly presented in the works of bestselling contemporary authors, such as Colleen Hoover.

To address this gap, this study examines how personal, familial, moral, and social issues are reflected in selected novels by Colleen Hoover. It focuses on how these issues are portrayed through character development, symbolism, and the life lessons embedded in the narratives. The findings aim to demonstrate how literature can reflect real-life circumstances and help readers understand the challenges people face in order to survive. This study is significant because it highlights the relevance of contemporary literature in promoting emotional awareness, empathy, and insight into the human condition.

2. Literature Review

Mohammad and Anis (2024) examine the trauma of Lily Bloom in *It Ends with Us* by analyzing her personality, attitudes, and behaviors, especially in relation to her father and intimate relationships. Their study shows that Lily's emotional responses and life decisions are shaped by repeated and prolonged domestic violence, which manifests in her behavioral patterns and coping mechanisms. They argue that the types of trauma Lily experienced are deeply embedded in her character development and actions throughout the novel.

However, the study of Ismail, Aliaa, and Marwan (2025) focuses on the character of Ryle, who, despite being abusive, is romanticized by many readers. They explain this response through psychological factors, including the fundamental attribution error, the mere exposure effect, personal schemas, and repressed aggressive tendencies. Their findings suggest that some readers externalize or justify Ryle's harmful behavior, which plays a role in the continued literary and social appeal of "toxic" male characters.

Similarly, Esi, Tahrin, and Masagus (2024) identify several moral and emotional values present in Hoover's narratives, such as modesty, honesty, affection, bravery, kindness, and sincerity. According to their study, these intrinsic elements contribute to Hoover's novels being compelling and relatable for readers across different countries, as they reflect universal emotional experiences.

Based on these studies, the present research assumes that Colleen Hoover's novels reflect personal, family, moral, and social issues that resonate with real-life situations. This study is grounded in Stephen Greenblatt's New Historicism and Roland Barthes's Reader-Response Theory. New Historicism emphasizes the relationship between literature and the social, cultural, and political conditions of its time, highlighting how texts both shape and are shaped by structures of power (Greenblatt 1980). In this context, Hoover's works can be understood as narratives influenced by contemporary discussions on trauma, women's agency, and the cycle of abuse. Her novels reflect how patriarchal systems may disguise violence as love or stability, revealing the cultural dynamics surrounding romanticized power imbalances.

Reader-Response Theory, as advanced by Barthes (1977), argues that meaning is not solely determined by the author but is actively created by the reader. Barthes asserts that the "death of the author" signifies a shift in interpretive authority, where the reader's experiences, emotions, and cultural background shape how a text is understood. Therefore, Hoover's narratives may be interpreted differently by readers depending on their personal perspectives, beliefs, and experiences with issues like those depicted in the novels. The meaning of the text is not fixed; instead, it emerges through the reader's engagement and interpretation.

3. Research Methodology

Research Design

This study employs a qualitative research design, using discourse analysis as its primary method. Qualitative research focuses on interpreting meanings found in texts rather than numerical data, examining how language constructs social realities and conveys experiences. Discourse analysis examines how written or spoken language functions within its social context, aiming to explain how meaning is produced, interpreted, and circulated in real-life situations (Scribbr, 2023). Through this method, the study examines the personal, family, moral, and social issues reflected in Colleen Hoover's novels, with a focus on character development, symbolism, and the expression of life values. The analysis is guided by Stephen Greenblatt's New Historicism, which views texts as products of cultural and historical forces, and Roland Barthes's Reader-Response Theory, which emphasizes the role of the reader in constructing meaning.

Sources of Data

The primary source of data is Colleen Hoover's novel *It Ends with Us* (2016), which consistently ranked in the Top 100 and Top 20 Adult Print Bestsellers in the United States. Its widespread readership and cultural impact make it a suitable text for examining issues relevant to contemporary lived experiences. Secondary sources include scholarly articles, books, magazines, newspapers, and credible online materials that provide theoretical perspectives, contextual information, and supporting interpretations.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was conducted in three phases, following the procedures of discourse analysis. Lines and narrative elements from the novel were identified, categorized, and interpreted using the selected theoretical lenses.

- Phase 1: Character Analysis. This phase involved examining dialogue, descriptions, and character interactions to identify expressions of personal, family, moral, and social issues. Extracted text segments were analyzed in relation to character behavior and development, supported by related literature.

- Phase 2: Symbolism Analysis. This phase examined objects, events, or recurring imagery that symbolize deeper emotional, cultural, or social meanings. These symbolisms were interpreted in connection to the identified issues, with explanations supported by theoretical references and prior studies.
- Phase 3: Life Values Analysis. This phase focused on identifying themes and life values conveyed in the text. The analysis determined how these values reflect or respond to personal and societal challenges, again drawing on supporting literature and theoretical insights.

4. Analysis and Discussion

Character

The characters in the novel undertake intense personal efforts to manage their circumstances, particularly those rooted in trauma, love, and personal growth. Lily Bloom is working through pain to break the cycle, and her life circumstances are shaped by an abusive childhood from her father, who abused her mother, and she carried the emotional scars of watching her mother suffer in silence. Then her toxic romantic relationship, when Ryle, her partner, becomes abusive, she is forced to confront her past mirrors her present. Lily chose to do the hard emotional labor of recognizing that love is not enough when violence is involved. She reflects on her past to avoid repeating it, makes the painful decision to leave Ryle, and raises her child alone while staying emotionally intense. The line, “It stops here. With me and you. It ends with us,” shows Lily’s deliberate choice to change the course of her life and her child, which is the heart of human work on life’s circumstances.

Ryle Kincaid is the tragedy of unresolved trauma and he is shaped by his own unresolved trauma when he accidentally killed his brother as a child, which left deep psychological scars. Ryle does not do enough of the emotional labor needed to manage his trauma. He tries to bury the pain rather than work through it, and he loses control when emotionally triggered, leading to abuse. His character demonstrates what happens when the necessary personal work is avoided or denied – how pain can spill over and harm those around him.

Atlas Corrigan is working through abandonment to become safe and stable. As he is Lily's first love, he faced homelessness and neglect as a teenager and emotional rejection, and social stigma. The Atlas journey is one of perseverance and self-discipline. He works hard to build a stable life, becomes a successful restaurant owner, and learns to love Lily from a healthy, respectful distance until she is ready. His progress demonstrates how human resilience in the face of challenging life circumstances can lead to healing and stability.

The novel is a powerful exploration of how characters respond to their life circumstances through emotional work, self-reflection, and hard decisions. The novel suggests that we may not be able to choose our circumstances, but we can choose to respond by engaging in the human work of healing, growth, and change, which is essential for breaking harmful cycles and building a better life. The characters illustrate that while life circumstances may be difficult, it is the work we do on ourselves that defines our future.

Theme

The novel explores how characters actively work through pain, trauma, love, and self-identity to change the course of their lives. The novel's central theme is breaking the cycle of abuse, generational abuse, and the struggle to break free from it. Lily must confront the reality that her partner, Ryle, mirrors the abusive behavior of her father. She does the difficult inner work of recognizing patterns and choosing not to normalize or excuse them. Her decision to leave Ryle, even though she loves him, represents the painful but empowering human labor of ending the cycle for her and her daughter. The line, "Just because someone hurts you doesn't mean you can simply stop loving them." This shows the emotional complexity of Lily's decision and the mental strength required to act against ingrained emotional patterns.

The novel explores the tension between love versus self-respect. Lily must choose between her deep love for Ryle and her need to protect herself and her child. She works to redefine love not as blind loyalty, but as mutual respect and safety. The inner conflict she experiences highlights the difficulty of prioritizing self-worth in a relationship that is emotionally powerful yet dangerous.

Forgiveness is a significant theme, not to excuse behavior, but to heal. Lily forgives her mother for staying in an abusive marriage, understanding her limitations. She also reaches a place of understanding with Ryle, not to reconcile but to co-parent peacefully. Forgiveness here requires deep emotional work, empathy, and letting go of anger without surrendering personal boundaries.

The strength and independence to build one's own path, emotionally and practically, is celebrated in the novel. Lily creates a business, maintains her friendships, and prepares to raise a child. Her independence is not hounded to her; it is the result of determination, resilience, and emotional clarity. The line, "There is no such thing as bad people. We are all just people who sometimes do bad things." This reflects Lily's balanced, mature worldview, born from introspection and lived experience.

The novel shows how trauma affects behavior and relationships. Ryle's trauma (his brother's death) is never fully addressed, leading to violent outbursts. The contrast between Ryle and Lily (who confronts her trauma) emphasizes the importance of working through emotional pain rather than ignoring it. The narrative encourages readers to recognize that trauma is not an excuse, but rather something that demands personal responsibility and healing.

The novel challenges readers to understand that meaningful change, whether in breaking cycles, building self-respect, or finding healing, requires deep, often painful personal labor. Colleen Hoover's characters illustrate that while life circumstances may be difficult, it is the work we do on ourselves that defines our future.

Symbolism

In 'It Ends with Us' by Colleen Hoover, symbolism plays a powerful role in expressing deeper meanings about trauma, love, resilience, and transformation. The emotional, mental, and moral labor characters undertake to change their lives is deeply connected to these symbols. Each symbolic element reflects the inner journey of the characters, highlighting the work required to grow and heal.

The flower shop "Lily Blooms" symbolizes growth, rebirth, and self-reliance. Flowers bloom under care and patience, just as people do. Lily

builds a business from the ground up, symbolizing the work she's doing on herself. She utilizes creativity and determination to transform her dream into a tangible reality, which reflects her emotional growth. The shops represent her independence and her effort to establish a life separate from pain and trauma. Her nurturing of the shop mirrors her inner growth; tending to both requires hard work, vision, and resilience.

The name Lily Bloom is itself symbolic. Lilies often represent purity, renewal, and strength. Lily's name isn't just a label – it is a metaphor for her journey. She blooms through hardship by making difficult but empowering choices. Her transformation from a woman stuck in a toxic pattern to one who breaks the cycle is like a flower blooming in harsh conditions.

The magnet Atlas gives Lily a symbol of an unbreakable connection and safety, something real and grounded amid chaos. Lily holds onto the magnet as a token of hope, stability, and a love that once sheltered her during a traumatic time. It serves as a reminder of what love without harm feels like, helping her mentally compare her past with her present. The magnet is not about romantic idealism – it is a symbol of emotional truth that she must work to recognize and trust again.

The journal entries to Ellen DeGeneres represent Lily's need to process her emotions safely and privately, especially during times of emotional chaos. Writing these letters is a form of self-therapy. She reflects deeply on her life, her pain, and her relationships. This symbolic act of writing demonstrates how healing requires time, reflection, and the confrontation of truth without denial. The journals demonstrate the ongoing work of emotional honesty, noticing patterns, facing pain, and narrating your own story.

The phrase “It Ends with Us” is Lily's declaration that the cycle of abuse will stop with her. Saying it ends with us takes immense emotional strength. Lily makes this decision for her daughter's sake, showing that the future can be different but only through conscious effort. It symbolizes the culmination of all the human work Lily does in recognizing abuse, working away, and choosing peace over pain. It is not just a title; it is a symbol of legacy, sacrifice, and personal evolution. Colleen Hoover employs these symbols not only as literary devices but also as emotional mirrors that reflect the process of becoming whole.

Life Values

The novel doesn't just tell a story of love and heartbreak; it shows how people can work through hardships to discover and live by stronger values. Courage is the strength to do what is right and not what is easy. Sometimes love means letting go. True courage is doing what is necessary to protect yourself and others, even when it hurts. Lily's decision to leave Ryle despite still loving him is an act of profound courage. She has mentally and emotionally pushed against the instinct to stay, which requires confronting fear, heartbreak, and social pressure. "It stops here. With me and you. It ends with us." This is Lily's declaration of strength, showing that courage is a daily decision, not a one-time act.

Self-respect is knowing your worth and setting boundaries. Self-respect is non-negotiable in any relationship. Lily learns to prioritize her own safety and emotional well-being over her romantic attachment. She sets firm boundaries with Ryle, even when others might expect forgiveness or reconciliation. This teaches readers that self-respect requires inner work, such as learning to say no even to people you care about when your values are at risk.

Empathy is understanding without excusing. We can have compassion for someone's pain without accepting harmful behavior. Lily shows empathy toward Ryle, acknowledging that his trauma influences his actions. But she also understands that empathy does not mean accepting abuse. This emotional maturity demonstrates a balance between compassion and accountability, a difficult yet essential value to practice.

Healing is growth through pain. Healing is not about forgetting pain, but about learning from it and growing stronger. Lily doesn't rush her healing. She allows herself to feel grief, anger, and confusion. She seeks peace through journaling, self-reflection, and surrounding herself with supportive people, such as Atlas. Healing, the novel teaches us, is a process, an act of daily human effort to choose progress over perfection.

It Ends with Us teaches that life values like courage, self-respect, empathy, and healing are not innate – they are built through human effort. Every choice Lily makes demonstrates how hard emotional labor can lead to strength and transformation. Readers are reminded that doing

the right thing is rarely easy, but always worth it, especially when it means protecting your future and redefining your worth.

Implications

The novel humanizes both the victim and the abuser, showing how abuse isn't always clear-cut or easy to escape. The story highlights the power and pain of breaking free from generational patterns. It also highlights how society often questions victims instead of supporting them. The book complicates the idea of romantic love. Healing from trauma isn't linear, and strength can co-exist with vulnerability. The novel raises awareness and brings visibility to issues that many shy away from discussing. It Ends with Us isn't just a novel—it is a narrative that speaks to real pain, survival, and the quiet strength it takes to break free. It is most potent in saying that change begins with individual choices, even when those choices are heart-wrenchingly painful. The study's implication is purely emotional and social consciousness related to domestic violence and the complex psychology behind abusive relationships.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

The novel is a compelling and emotionally charged exploration of complex themes, including love, abuse, resilience, and personal growth. Through its deeply relatable characters and the raw narrative, the novel sheds light on the often-painful life circumstances of domestic violence and the difficult choices victims face. Hoover encourages empathy and understanding, making significant contributions to contemporary romance and social issues in literature. The study recommends exploring the psychological and social impact of the novel on readers, particularly in terms of how it influences their perceptions of domestic abuse and empowerment. Educators and counselors might also consider incorporating this novel into discussions about relationships and abuse to foster dialogue and awareness.

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Informed Consent

The authors declare that informed consent was not required, as no human participants were involved.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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